

Studies on Infrared Spectra of *O,O*-Bisaryl Isopropyl Phosphonates

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INFRARED spectrophotometry gives characteristic peaks for the identification of organophosphorus compounds, which are being increasingly used as insecticides and fungicides. We present here our studies on the ir spectra of *O,O*-bisaryl isopropyl phosphonates, a new class of fungicides developed by us¹.

Experimental

Details regarding the synthesis, purification and pmr studies have been described elsewhere^{1,2}. The ir spectra (CCl₄) were obtained by a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectrum of the parent compound *O,O*-bisphenyl isopropyl phosphonate (1) shows characteristic peaks³ at 910 (P-O stretching of P-O-C aromatic), 1 200 (C-O stretching of P-O-C

aromatic), 1 280 (P-O) with an adjacent peak at 1 255 and 675 cm⁻¹ (P-C). The frequencies corresponding to these vibrations for all the compounds are given in Table 1.

From Table 1, it appears that there is no correlation between frequency and the nature of phenyl substituents. Even in the case of frequency corresponding to C-O stretching of P-O-C (aromatic), which is directly connected to the phenyl ring, there appears to be no correlation between frequency and the electronic nature or molecular weight of substituents. Since many substituents are polyatomic, vibrations within the group might be affecting the C-O stretching making it difficult to get good correlations.

Eliminating all compounds with polyatomic substituents and considering compounds 1, 2, 3, 19 and 20, there appeared a strong correlation between frequency and electronic nature of the substituent represented by Hammett's parameter as shown by the equation,

$$\nu_{C-O \text{ stretch}} = 1203 + 27.8 \Sigma\sigma \quad (1)$$

$$n = 5,$$

$$r = 0.98$$

In the above equation, $\Sigma\sigma$ is the Hammett's electronic parameter⁴ obtained by simple additivity of σ_p and σ_m from literature and presuming $\sigma_p = \sigma_o$. Values for all the compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF *O,O*-BISARYL ISOPROPYL PHOSPHONATES

Compd. no.	Nature of substitution	$\Sigma\sigma$	P-O vibration			P-O-C (Ar) C-O stretch	P-O stretch	P-C stretch
			(i)	(ii)	Difference			
1	Nil	0.00	1 280	1 255	25	1 200	910	675
2	2-Cl	0.23	1 290	1 260	30	1 210	925	675
3	4-Cl	0.23	1 285	1 260	25	1 210	910	680
4	2-OCH ₃	-0.27	1 285	1 250	35	1 200	925	680
5	4-OCH ₃	-0.27	1 280	1 260	20	1 200	925	685
6	2-CH ₃	-0.17	1 280	1 255	25	1 210	920	680
7	3-CH ₃	-0.07	1 280	1 250	30	1 210	920	685
8	4-CH ₃	-0.17	1 280	1 260	20	1 210	920	680
9	2-NO ₂	0.78	1 290	1 260	30	1 220	920	680
10	4-NO ₂	0.78	1 285	1 255	30	1 220	915	675
11	4-C(CH ₃) ₃	-0.20	1 285	1 255	30	1 220	920	682
12	4-SCH ₃	0.00	1 290	1 260	30	1 215	915	685
13	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	-0.24	1 295	Absent	N.A.	1 220	930	680
14	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	-0.34	1 290	1 260	30	1 240	915	670
15	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	-0.24	1 280	Absent	N.A.	1 230	945	670
16	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	-0.24	1 275	1 255	20	1 225	945	685
17	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	-0.14	1 275	1 255	20	1 235	950	675
18	2,3,5-(CH ₃) ₃	-0.31	1 275	1 255	20	1 240	930	680
19	2,4,5-Cl ₃	0.83	1 280	1 255	25	1 230	935	680
20	2,3,4,5,6-Cl ₅	1.43	1 292	1 255	37	1 240	925	700

N.A. = Not applicable.

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NOTES

Even when compounds 8 and 9 were included, the following equation with a good correlation coefficient could be obtained.

$$\nu_{\text{C-O stretch}} = 1202 + 26.7 \Sigma \sigma \quad (2)$$

$$n = 7,$$

$$r = 0.97$$

The correlation coefficients of equations (1) and (2) are quite significant, but the result should be considered only indicative since the compounds under consideration are quite few.

The phosphoryl vibration of the parent compound *O,O*-bisphenyl isopropyl phosphonate appears as a doublet where two adjacent vibrations at 1280 and 1255 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to this vibration, were observed. This doublet was observed in cases of all compounds except 13 and 15. Earlier investigators had concluded that the doublets can arise from two conformers with different phosphoryl vibrations⁵ or due to the accidental proximity of a band ascribed to different vibrations in the molecule⁶. It was found that when the doublet is characterised by small differences in frequency and intensity between component peaks and when the doublet is not being fully resolved, these arose from two conformers with different phosphoryl vibration³. By contrast, in those spectra in which the doublet arose from accidental proximity of a band ascribed to a different vibration in the molecule, the peaks were separated maximum upto 50 cm^{-1} with a well defined minimum between them³. In the case of bisaryl isopropyl phosphonates presently investigated, there appears no well-defined minimum between adjacent peaks, and the frequency between the peaks varies from 20 to 40 cm^{-1} . In many cases they are characterised by small differences in intensity, sometimes not being fully resolved (compounds 13–15). Therefore, it can be concluded that the doublets arose from two conformers with different phosphoryl vibration frequencies and not from accidental proximity of a band ascribed to a different vibration.

An absorption band at 1300 cm^{-1} in the case of bisaryl methyl phosphonates and other compounds⁷ containing P–Me groups were ascribed to P–C stretching by some workers⁷. The absence of any such peak at 1300 cm^{-1} for bisaryl isopropyl phosphonates confirms the view that these were normal C–H deformation vibrations the frequency of which has been perturbed by the presence of phosphorus³.

References

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¹³C NMR and Crystallographic Evidence for Steric Enhancement of Resonance in 2-Alkylanisoles

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ALTHOUGH steric enhancement of resonance (SER) has been studied in 4-nitro-2-substituted-anisoles¹, 4-acetyl-2-substituted-anisoles² and other 2,4-substituted anisoles³, its existence in 2-alkylanisoles has not been made known. When a powerful electron-withdrawing substituent is present *para* to the methoxyl, the resonance interaction between the *para*-substituents will be high and the enhancement of resonance caused by a substituent like methyl or a halogen atom *ortho* to the methoxyl is considerable. Its detection in such cases is also easy. In the absence of a powerful electron-attracting group *para* to the methoxyl, the SER caused by an *ortho*-substituent will be feeble and its detection requires more exact observations and more sophisticated experimental measurements. For example, Dhami and Stothers⁴ failed to observe it in the ¹³C nmr spectra of 2-alkylanisoles and they even expressed doubt about the existence of SER.

We now have convincing evidence for the SER in 2-alkylanisoles from the ¹³C nmr data published by Schuster *et al.*⁵ recently. The data are given in Table 1. It may be seen that all the 2-alkylanisoles (2–5; Table 1), show increased electron

TABLE 1—SCS-CORRECTED^a ¹³C CHEMICAL SHIFTS^b OF THE *para*-CARBON IN SUBSTITUTED-ANISOLE^s*

Compd. no.	Substituent	δ
1	Nil	120.64
2	2-Methyl	120.04
3	2-Ethyl	120.12
4	2- <i>i</i> -Propyl	120.30
5	2- <i>t</i> -Butyl	120.29
6	2,6-Dimethyl	123.39
7	2,6-Diethyl	123.53
8	2,6-Di- <i>i</i> -propyl	123.86
9	2,6-Di- <i>t</i> -butyl	122.91
10	2- <i>t</i> -Butyl-6-methyl	122.49

*Data from Ref. 5.

^aObtained by subtracting the substituent chemical shift (SCS) of the *meta*-oriented alkyl group R or groups R and R (with reference to C₄) from the experimental value. SCS = $\delta \{^{13}\text{C}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{R})\} - 128.31$ ppm (L. Ernst, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 3079). ^bIn ppm from Me₄Si.

density at the C-4 carbon atom (upfield shift) compared with anisole due to enhanced resonance. In